

Application of fastText One Versus All Loss for Coding Multiple Response Data in the Canadian Census

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Abstract

Many questions in the Canadian census require the respondent to provide a written response in an open text field. These responses are then processed by matching the written response to a numeric code, a process referred to as "coding". While most of these variables require a single response, some census questions allow the respondent to provide more than one answer. This coding of write-in responses is done in part using machine learning with the fastText algorithm. This presents a particularly interesting problem as machine learning algorithms, including the default fastText application, provide one label (or code) per record where we may desire multiple. To solve this issue, we explored the application of the fastText One Versus All (OVA) loss function, which treats each label as a separate binary classification problem, thus enabling the model to predict multiple labels simultaneously. By employing this approach, we aimed to demonstrate the effectiveness of the OVA loss function in accurately predicting multiple labels associated with our response data, and the improvement we could obtain in comparison to our previous method.

Key Words: fastText, multi-label classification, natural language processing, coding

1. Introduction

1.1 The Coding Process

In the Canadian census, some questions allow the respondent to provide responses that are different from the available response options. For example, the question “*What language(s) does this person speak on a regular basis at home?*” offers three options: *English*, *French*, and *Other language(s) – specify*. Respondents who choose the third option will provide answers in their own words, which are referred to as write-ins. These write-in responses must go through a process during which they are assigned to numeric values, also known as codes. This process of assigning codes to write-ins is referred to as coding at Statistics Canada and in this document. To facilitate this process, reference files are created to serve as dictionaries containing common and expected write-ins and their corresponding codes.

The traditional coding process contains three main steps, namely: auto-coding, interactive coding, and code-fix. Auto-coding is the first step where write-ins can be matched to entries in the reference files. Most write-ins from respondents already exist in the reference files and can be automatically assigned codes through this process. Typically, this step has high accuracy and records which are auto-coded will go on directly to the third step - code-fix. There are, however, write-ins from respondents which fail to receive codes during auto-coding and thus require manual intervention. These records go through the second process, interactive coding, where a team of temporary employees, hired during each census cycle, manually code these records. Interactive coding can be

time consuming, costly and error prone. The third step, code-fix, happens concurrently with the other steps, where subject matter experts spend a significant amount of time reviewing codes assigned from the other stages and applying corrections as needed.

To alleviate some of the issues with interactive coding described above, for the 2021 Census, machine learning models were introduced into the coding process to replace as much interactive coding as possible. A natural language processing algorithm developed by Facebook called fastText, capable of performing text classification, was implemented to achieve this.

1.2 Multiple Response Variables and the Previous Method

Of the questions which offer write-ins, some allow respondents to provide more than one answer when applicable. For these types of questions, several write-in spaces are provided to record each answer from the respondent. Each write-in is stored as a separate column on our response database. In the past, an interactive coder would view all these columns together for a given respondent, allowing the interactive coder to easily decide the number of codes and which ones to assign by combining the information received. On the contrary, since each write-in space is stored separately, when applying fastText under the default loss function the algorithm would provide exactly one code per write-in space. As will be shown in some examples, this is a potential drawback of using the default loss function of fastText compared to interactive coding, which motivated this project in search of a solution.

Ideally, the respondent would provide exactly one answer per write-in space and each answer would receive one code. However, respondents sometimes provide more than one answer in a single write-in space or provide a single answer over multiple write-in spaces. Below is an example of such a question which asks about the ethnic or cultural origins of a respondent. In this question, four spaces of eleven characters are available on the paper questionnaire as shown in Figure 1. Each space will correspond to a column in our response data base once the data is collected.

23 What were the ethnic or cultural origins of this person's **ancestors**?

Ancestors may have Indigenous origins, or origins that refer to different countries, or other origins that may not refer to different countries.

For examples of ethnic or cultural origins, visit www12.statcan.gc.ca/ancestry

Specify as many origins as applicable using capital letters.

Figure 1: 2021 Census Question of Ethnic or cultural origins

An example of an ideal response is shown in Figure 1.1. Here, the response would be GERMAN, AUSTRIAN, GREEK, ITALIAN, each on its own line. Stored separately in our database, fastText under the default loss function would be able to provide a single code for each response.

23 What were the ethnic or cultural origins of this person's **ancestors**?

Ancestors may have Indigenous origins, or origins that refer to different countries, or other origins that may not refer to different countries.

For examples of ethnic or cultural origins, visit www12.statcan.gc.ca/ancestry

Specify as many origins as applicable using capital letters.

G	R	E	E	K							
I	T	A	L	I	A	N					

Figure 1.1: An Ideal Response

Figure 1.2 shows an example of multiple answers within one write-in space. This type of answer is potentially problematic because it corresponds to two (in this example) or more (in some other cases) codes but would only receive one code under the default loss function.

23 What were the ethnic or cultural origins of this person's ancestors?

Ancestors may have Indigenous origins, or origins that refer to different countries, or other origins that may not refer to different countries.

For examples of ethnic or cultural origins, visit www12.statcan.gc.ca/ancestry

Specify as many origins as applicable using capital letters.

USA CANADA

Figure 1.2: Multiple Responses in One Space

Another type of answer contains one response, but it is filled in over more than one write-in space. Figure 1.3 shows such an example. This response corresponds to one code only but would receive two using the default loss function as fastText would see “UNITED,” and “KINGDOM” separately and assign two different codes.

23 What were the ethnic or cultural origins of this person's ancestors?

Ancestors may have Indigenous origins, or origins that refer to different countries, or other origins that may not refer to different countries.

For examples of ethnic or cultural origins, visit www12.statcan.gc.ca/ancestry

Specify as many origins as applicable using capital letters.

UNITED

KINGDOM

Figure 1.3: One Response over Multiple Spaces

Finally, a case could occur where a respondent answers the question with sentences containing extraneous words. An example of this type of response is shown below in Figure 1.4. This response only contains two meaningful words and should receive two codes, one for ITALIAN and one for GREEK. However, the presence of these extraneous words causes a problem as fastText under the default loss function would see each line separately and assign four codes while a human coder could easily see that this should be only two codes.

23 What were the ethnic or cultural origins of this person's ancestors?

Ancestors may have Indigenous origins, or origins that refer to different countries, or other origins that may not refer to different countries.

For examples of ethnic or cultural origins, visit www12.statcan.gc.ca/ancestry

Specify as many origins as applicable using capital letters.

MY MOTHER

IS ITALIAN

MY FATHER

IS GREEK

Figure 1.4: One Response with Extraneous Words over Multiple Spaces

Due to these unintended ways of responding to multiple response questions, using the default loss function of fastText, and assigning one code per write-in space is not the best approach as it would only work well for ideal responses. During the 2021 Census, a solution was devised to accurately code all such scenarios. This solution was to process each word from a write-in response by fastText under the default loss function as opposed to each line. This meant that we would provide every

word within a response a code, including words that did not contain meaningful information. This solution could work well for some cases such as the first and second one, but less so for the latter two. For instance, in cases such as “UNITED KINGDOM,” written over two spaces, it would receive two codes instead of one. Another issue with this kind of response is that there is no way to differentiate between “UNITED” in “UNITED STATES” and “UNITED KINGDOM.” For cases containing extraneous words such as the fourth example, this solution would result in eight codes in total including non-meaningful codes for words such as “MY”, “MOTHER”, “FATHER”, and “IS”, which makes little sense and would require cleanup of codes by subject matter experts who would attempt to keep only the meaningful codes during the code-fix process. Thus, while this method worked for most cases, it was inelegant and an alternative approach for the 2026 Census was sought.

The goal of this research project is to explore the feasibility of using an alternative approach to the one used in 2021. Specifically, using an alternative loss function within fastText called One Versus All (OVA) which can assign multiple codes to a single write-in. This approach has the potential to improve quality and reduce the reliance on manual intervention by subject matter experts. In this document, we will discuss in more detail the multiple response variables, the proposed method, and our results for the variables analyzed.

2. 2021 Canadian Census Data Preprocessing

The research was performed using three variables from the 2021 Canadian Census: Ethnic or Cultural Origins, Citizenship, and Knowledge of Non-Official Languages. As mentioned in the last section, there exist meaningless words in many responses and the previous method inevitably produced some undesirable codes for these responses. In most cases, the non-meaningful words were anticipated and assigned specific codes. However, this was not always the case: occasionally, non-meaningful words that were not anticipated and similar to the variable of interest may have received valid meaningful codes. The cleanup of the anticipated non-meaningful codes was straightforward, but the cleanup of the other ones was not and required extensive manual intervention. These non-meaningful codes were not desirable for our model training purposes because we did not want to teach the model inaccurate knowledge of these extraneous words. Thus, the remaining codes representing extraneous words had to be removed prior to model training.

The experiment was conducted using two approaches to data cleaning. The first cleaning method simply removed non-meaningful codes that were anticipated if at least one valid code existed. The second method followed an editing step from our edit and imputation procedure. The resulting data would be cleaner than the one from the first method since more meaningless codes would have been removed during editing. However, it is possible that it could in fact be too clean as perhaps some deterministic edits could have occurred which went beyond what was required for our purposes. We therefore assessed two versions of the fastText OVA method: one using data from the first cleaning method which may be slightly noisy due to extraneous codes, and the other one using data from the second method with potentially the opposite issue of being too sanitized. Rather than training the models to predict codes for each of the write-in spaces separately, we chose instead to concatenate all the write-ins for each of the variables we analyzed. We judged this approach to be more appropriate since we wish to include all meaningful information and avoid cases such as the second example. Therefore, we arrange our data so that there is one string containing all the write-ins concatenated and one string that contains all codes.

Additionally, we also kept track of how each write-in component was coded. If all write-in values from a respondent before concatenation were all auto-coded individually, then after concatenation, this record is flagged as fully auto-coded. On the other hand, if write-in values prior to concatenation were a combination of auto-coding and the previous machine learning method, then this record will be flagged as not fully auto-coded. An example of a fully auto-coded record might be “ENGLISH FRENCH.” Both ENGLISH and FRENCH appear in the reference file and thus would be auto-coded. An example of a record that is not fully auto-coded would be “ENGLISH FRCH,” where FRCH is not spelled correctly and would not appear in the reference file and thus that portion of the write-in would have been coded by machine learning in the previous census. The concepts of fully

auto-coded and not fully auto-coded will be used in the sections to come. The following subsections describe the peculiarities of the data for each of the variables we analyzed, as well as the steps taken to prepare the data using both cleaning methods.

2.1 Ethnic Origin

The ethnic origin question provides four spaces for the respondent to list their ethnic or cultural origin. The first cleaning method removed codes based on the following rules for each record: if each of the different values of a record is coded to a non-meaningful code, then only one non-meaningful code is assigned to this record; if some codes refer to non-informative while others do not, we remove the non-informative ones and retain the rest; if all codes are valid, we keep them as they are. As a result of concatenation, some records may still have a mix of valid codes and non-informative ones. Following the final deterministic edit and imputation step for the ethnic origin variable, the second method produced a maximum of six codes for each respondent, some of which may correspond to blank, not-applicable, or invalid write-ins.

2.2 Citizenship

The citizenship variable contains two write-in values. In this case, extraneous words were already accounted for during the previous coding process, as if the first cleaning method had already been applied. Thus, the codes for this variable did not need to be cleaned again by the first method prior to training the model. The second cleaning method was applied and produced at most four codes per record for this variable, following a step from the edit and imputation procedure.

2.3 Knowledge of Non-Official Languages

The knowledge of non-official languages variable contains four write-in values. Like the citizenship variable, the first cleaning method was not necessary for the same reason. The second cleaning method used a simplified version of the first step from our edit and imputation procedure to prevent over processing. At most sixteen codes per record for non-official languages were produced.

3. Proposed Method and Model Selection

By default, the loss function in fastText is the SoftMax function, which is a single classifier that assigns a “probability” to each label. Under this loss function, the probabilities must sum to one and the label with the highest probability is chosen, resulting in a single label (code) per write-in. In contrast to the default SoftMax function, the OVA loss function provides independent binary classifiers for each label so that each label receives a probability between 0 and 1. Then, any label with a probability above a user determined threshold would be retained, allowing for multiple codes per response. By concatenating write-ins from all spaces before applying fastText with the OVA loss function, we allow the algorithm to provide multiple codes per response, potentially leading to better results with less manual intervention.

This section describes the model selection procedure that was used for all datasets. These datasets are quite large with millions of records available for use as training data. Thus, we determined that a k-fold cross validation was not necessary for hyperparameter selection. Instead, we could simply perform a train-validation step to select the optimal hyperparameters. Therefore, we split each dataset into approximately 60% for training, 20% for validation, and 20% for final testing. To prevent data leakage due to one person responding for multiple people within a household, we kept records from the same household in the same set.

The hyperparameters in fastText are: wordNgrams, minn, maxn, learning rate (lr), lrUpdateRate, dim, and epoch. For the use of OVA loss, a smaller value of learning rate is suggested. Additionally, when using the OVA loss function, a threshold must be specified. This threshold is the probability above which a label is assigned. Different values of this threshold may affect which labels and how many labels are assigned, which would in turn affect the “correctness” of the labeling. Nevertheless, we chose 0.5 as the threshold since the space of hyperparameters is already large and adding another dimension would only make random search less efficient. Another consideration was that we wanted

to minimize the number of records which do not receive any labels due to not having any labels above the threshold, since every record must be assigned at least one label during our actual census production. Even at 0.5, some records still did not receive any labels. For those records, we would have to either choose the label with the highest probability or assign a code representing “not coded” and have them be reviewed by subject matter experts in code-fix. Twenty-five sets of hyperparameters were randomly sampled from the following possible values:

Table 1: Range of fastText Hyperparameters

	<i>wordNgrams</i>	<i>minn</i>	<i>maxn</i>	<i>lr</i>	<i>lrUpdateRate</i>	<i>dim</i>	<i>epoch</i>
Minimum	1	2	2	0.1	50	50	5
Maximum	4	6	6	0.7	150	350	35
Increment	1	1	1	0.01	1	1	1

A metric of selection must be determined when a model is evaluated. Since this is a classification problem of multiple classes and multiple labels, record-wise evaluation cannot be based only on the number of correct labels but also on the number of incorrect labels. Class-wise evaluation should also be included. The metrics we considered were exact subset accuracy, Hamming loss, Jaccard index, and F1 score. Exact subset accuracy refers to the proportion of records whose predicted labels match exactly with their true labels. This is the strictest criterion. To measure the effect of falsely assigned labels by the model, we considered Hamming loss, which computes the proportion of the number of incorrectly assigned labels to total number of labels. A combination of exact subset accuracy and Hamming loss leads to Jaccard index, which is the proportion of correctly assigned labels over the union of true labels and predicted labels, penalizing false labels consequently. Once the validation step is completed, the optimal combination of hyperparameters is selected based on one of the above metrics and is used to train a final model on the entire 80% training data. In our experiment, we decided to use the Jaccard index as the selection metric, because it is a good balance between exact subset accuracy and Hamming loss.

4. Evaluation

Evaluation of machine learning models for the census is difficult. Although we have millions of labeled data available, the labels are not without error. Thus, comparing model predicted labels to a test set outright is not sufficient as it is impossible to discern if the model truly mis-predicted the label or if in fact the original label in the test set was incorrect. To account for this, we sampled two thousand records for subject matter experts to evaluate and decide what the ground truth should be. The sample size is small due to the nature of the reviewing process being very labor intensive but is sufficient for this evaluation.

These records were sampled randomly from either two strata or four strata. In the case of two strata, we divided the test dataset into a fully auto-coded portion and a not fully auto-coded portion. In the case of four strata, we further divided the two strata by whether the predicted codes from the fastText OVA model using the first cleaning method match the codes from the test set with the first cleaning method itself. As a result, we obtain the following four strata: firstly, records that are fully auto-coded and have predicted codes matching the ones from the test set; secondly, records that are fully auto-coded but do not have predicted codes matching the ones from the test set; thirdly, records that are not fully auto-coded but have predicted codes matching the ones from the test set; and lastly, records that are not fully auto-coded and also do not have predicted codes matching the test set. The diagram below demonstrates the structure of the strata.

Figure 2: Strata of the sample

In our analysis, we wanted to put the most emphasis on records whose predicted codes do not match the test set and considerable emphasis on records that were not fully auto-coded. Therefore, we chose different sample sizes for each stratum with significantly more records coming from these strata of interest. Detailed information of the sample sizes for different variables is documented in the results section. We provided our samples containing the concatenated write-in, original write-ins before concatenation, codes from the test set, codes produced from the previous method, and codes predicted by the proposed new method to different subject matter groups and asked them to provide the codes they believed were the truth.

Using codes by subject matter experts as the “ground truth,” we computed the evaluation metrics and compared the scores for the fastText with OVA loss method to the scores from the previous method before and after code-fix. We used sampling weights based on the stratified simple random sampling without replacement sample design to estimate the values of the evaluation metrics on the entire test set. Most of the metrics we considered are means, where the averaging is over records. Therefore, the weighted metrics could be computed as weighted averages, where the weights are given by the ratio of the strata size to the size of the test set that the sample was drawn from. The exception to this is the F1 Score, which was computed differently because it is not an arithmetic mean, but rather the harmonic mean of precision and recall. Since precision and recall are themselves arithmetic means over records, the weighted F1 score was computed as the harmonic mean of the weighted precision and weighted recall.

5. Results

In this section, we present our results for the three variables of interest. To provide a fair comparison for the fastText OVA and the previous method using SoftMax function, we include evaluation metrics for codes before and after code-fix with the subject matter codes as the ground truth. Furthermore, we provide results for each metric before and after weighting. We are interested in the results after weighting, as these are the estimated metrics for the entire test set. Nevertheless, it is still worth noting the results within the sample itself. Since the results did not differ significantly between the two methods of data cleaning, we will omit results from the second method for simplicity and clarity.

5.1 Ethnic or Cultural Origin

The sample for the ethnic or cultural origin variable comes from two strata, consisting of 400 fully auto-coded records and 1600 not fully auto-coded records, with weights of 0.9365 and 0.0635 for the two strata respectively using the proportion of the two strata in the test set. Table 1 demonstrates by row the comparison between the proposed new method using fastText OVA and the previous method using fastText SoftMax before and after code-fix. For each evaluation metric, we also included the results for the sample itself alongside with the estimated values for the test set after weighting. We can see that the fastText OVA method performs much better than the previous method without code-fix by any of the metrics. One obvious reason for this improvement is that by using fastText OVA, many codes for extraneous words are automatically excluded and records would only receive the meaningful codes correctly. Furthermore, the proposed method with fastText OVA outperforms the previous method using fastText with SoftMax even after code-fix. This implies that with the new method, we can potentially achieve even better results after code-fix.

Table 2: Results for Ethnic or Cultural Origin

	Exact Accuracy		Hamming Loss		Jaccard Index		F1 Score	
	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Weighted</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Weighted</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Weighted</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Weighted</i>
<i>fastText OVA</i>	0.8255	0.9447	0.0010	0.0004	0.8864	0.9611	0.9023	0.9655
<i>fastText SoftMax before Code-Fix</i>	0.4360	0.8977	0.0033	0.0006	0.6392	0.9288	0.7009	0.9408
<i>fastText SoftMax after Code-Fix</i>	0.7000	0.9187	0.0016	0.0004	0.8167	0.9419	0.8512	0.9520

5.2 Citizenship

The sample for the citizenship variable comes from four strata, consisting mostly of records that did not have predicted codes matching the test set, either fully auto-coded or not fully auto-coded. To estimate the overall performance, we use the following sampling weights for the four strata described in the previous section respectively: 0.9806, 0.0006, 0.0171, 0.0017. These weights were computed using the proportion of the four strata in the test set. Table 2 demonstrates the comparison between the proposed new method using fastText OVA and the previous method of fastText with SoftMax before and after code-fix. For this variable, there is an improvement over the previous method before code fix and the proposed method performs as well as the previous method plus code-fix. In this case, the fastText OVA method would still be preferable because it can achieve the same results without having to go through code-fix and could potentially see even greater gains in combination with code-fix.

Table 3: Results for Citizenship

	Exact Accuracy		Hamming Loss		Jaccard Index		F1 Score	
	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Weighted</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Weighted</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Weighted</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Weighted</i>
<i>fastText OVA</i>	0.6435	0.9960	0.0027	0.0003	0.7365	0.9972	0.7682	0.9977
<i>fastText SoftMax before Code-Fix</i>	0.5195	0.9872	0.0037	0.0010	0.6687	0.9910	0.7201	0.9929
<i>fastText SoftMax after Code-Fix</i>	0.7620	0.9968	0.0015	0.0002	0.8468	0.9979	0.8753	0.9985

5.3 Knowledge of Non-Official Languages

The sample for the knowledge of non-official languages variable also comes from four strata, consisting mostly of records that were not fully auto-coded and did not have predicted codes matching the test set, with weights for each stratum being 0.9418, 0.0014, 0.0497, 0.0072. Because the sample is very unbalanced, it is expected that the sample results would be poor. However, after weighting, this is no longer the case. From Table 3, we can see that there is an improvement over the previous method before code fix and the proposed method comes close to the previous method plus code-fix.

Table 4: Results for Knowledge of Non-Official Languages

	Exact Accuracy		Hamming Loss		Jaccard Index		F1 Score	
	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Weighted</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Weighted</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Weighted</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Weighted</i>
<i>fastText OVA</i>	0.1265	0.9694	0.0015	0.0004	0.4451	0.9831	0.5344	0.9896
<i>fastText SoftMax before Code-Fix</i>	0.4815	0.9572	0.0012	0.0007	0.6423	0.9741	0.6971	0.9818
<i>fastText SoftMax after Code-Fix</i>	0.7720	0.9750	0.0004	0.0003	0.8568	0.9867	0.8834	0.9925

6. Conclusion

The method used to code multiple-response questions for the previous census had several drawbacks, both in terms of quality and in terms of practicality of implementation. The proposed method using fastText with OVA loss is much more straight-forward to implement, more efficient, and at least equivalent in quality in most cases. Our research shows that this new method for coding responses to questions involving multiple responses offers a significant improvement over the previous method before code-fix in all cases and performs at least as well as the previous method after code-fix in some cases. With additional code-fix to the proposed method, even better results could be obtained.

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